

Criteria for Review of Root-Cause Analysis Programs

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Abstract: This paper describes the U.S. Nuclear Regulatory Commission's (NRC's) criteria for reviewing licensee root-cause analysis programs, as well as corrective action plans, and the methods that NRC inspectors can use to determine the adequacy of the programs. The specific criteria to be used for evaluating the licensee's root-cause analyses, corrective actions, and corrective action implementation plans are explained. Finally, evaluation criteria for communications-related events at nuclear power plants (NPPs) are given.

Keywords: Root-cause analysis, corrective actions, human performance errors, communications

I. INTRODUCTION

The criteria described in this paper are used by NRC personnel to evaluate root cause analysis programs and corrective actions involving human performance problems at NPPs. The purpose of these evaluations is to verify compliance with the

applicable requirements of Part 50 of Title 10 of the Code of Federal Regulations (10 CFR Part 50), Appendix B, Criterion XVI, "Corrective Action," which requires that licensees establish measures to ensure that conditions that degrade the quality of plant operations and safety shall be promptly identified and corrected. The evaluation criteria verify the following three elements:

- (1) The licensee's root-cause analysis demonstrates a thorough and complete understanding of the problems.
- (2) The licensee's process for the development of corrective actions ensures that the corrective actions address the root causes.
- (3) The licensee's program for assessing the implementation and effectiveness of the corrective actions is adequate.

II. EVALUATION CRITERIA

The criteria for the evaluation of root-cause analysis, corrective actions, and implementation of corrective action plans, follow. After each criteria some general guidance is given.

A. Root-Cause Analysis Criteria: Events at NPPs can arise from a wide variety of root causes. The effort and resources that a licensee dedicates to a root-cause analysis depend on numerous factors (e.g., more serious events should elicit more thorough analyses).

(1) *The root-cause analysis has considered an array of possible root causes.*

A root-cause analysis should investigate more than one possible explanation for an error.

(2) *The root-cause analysis has been derived from an events and causal-factors analysis.*

A thorough root-cause analysis should be derived from the following bases:

- A chart or an analysis depicting the relevant events and causal factors
- An analysis of the sequence of events that led to the error, as well as the causal factors that contributed to those events

An events and causal factors analysis is a graphic presentation of the sequence of events that led to an accident or an incident and the possible reasons (causal factors) for those events. The analysis helps the investigator to (a) understand the event progression, (b) identify lapses and inconsistencies in the information, and (c) explain the event to others.

(3) *The root-cause analysis used appropriate methods to investigate possible causes.*

The licensee should have determined the event causes using appropriate methods, such as the following:

- Interviews (face-to-face discussions)
- Barrier analysis (to identify the factors that, if avoided, would have prevented the event from occurring)
- Change analysis (a systematic approach for identifying changes in

the process that may have contributed to an event)

- Critical incident techniques (to identify critical actions that, if performed correctly, would have prevented the event from occurring or would have significantly reduced the event's consequences)
- Fault tree analysis (a qualitative or quantitative analysis that emphasizes the relationships among events and the probability of event occurrence)
- Human Performance Enhancement System (HPES-INPOs systematic investigation process) or Human Performance Investigation Process (HPIP-NRCs systematic investigation process)
- Management Oversight Risk Tree (MORT) (a systematic process using analytic techniques to determine the cause of problems)

Interviewing those involved in an event is the most common method used in root-cause analyses. However, information from interviews can be biased or limited in other ways. For example, people's memories of events are often faulty, and different individuals who have experienced the same event frequently remember it differently and give conflicting accounts. As another example, people have difficulty understanding and describing the factors that influence their behavior and decisions in general, and particularly in retrospect. Although interviews are a key source of information for root-cause analyses, the licensee should augment interview findings through the use of systematic event investigation tools such as those previously listed.

(4) *The basis for rejecting possible root causes has been documented.*

Reviewing the licensee's rationale for ruling out alternative possible root causes assists in ensuring the validity of the specific root causes identified. The evidence used to rule out alternatives will also be useful for future reference if events continue to occur after the licensee implements the corrective actions.

(5) *The root-cause analysis has identified and analyzed related events.*

Related events should be reviewed to determine the possible extent of the problem. Identifying other instances in which events have occurred and determining the causes for those events may reveal that the root causes for the event being investigated has had other effects. This information further validates the root causes identified. For problems involving human performance, "related" events may be defined as follows: (a) events involving personnel in the same job roles who perform the same tasks, (b) events involving personnel who have experienced the same type of training, (c) events involving personnel who work for the same supervisor, and (d) events that occurred while performing the same procedure.

(6) *A rationale for terminating the root-cause analysis has been documented.*

Causal analyses theoretically could progress without end. Alternatively, the analysis could stop as soon as only one cause is identified. If the analysis is terminated prematurely, the corrective actions will address only some of the problems and will not prevent future events from occurring.

(7) *The basis for the conclusions has been documented.*

The documentation ensures that conclusions are substantiated by facts that can be verified and will also be useful in future evaluations if a corrective action proves to be ineffective.

B. Development of Corrective Actions Criteria: The criteria for evaluation of the licensee's development of corrective actions follow:

(1) *The linkages have been specified between the root causes identified and the corrective actions proposed.*

It is necessary to verify that the relationship is established between identified root causes and the proposed corrective actions for events is established.

(2) *The licensee has identified the desired condition(s) that the corrective actions are intended to achieve.*

A desired condition is a statement of the goal that the corrective actions should achieve. A clear description of the desired condition serves at least three purposes: to assist NPP personnel in understanding why existing conditions are unacceptable, to describe the basis underlying the need for change, and to assist NPP workers in accepting new performance standards.

C. Corrective Action Implementation and Effectiveness Criteria: The criteria for evaluation of the licensee's program or plan for implementing the corrective actions and for monitoring/evaluating the effectiveness of the corrective actions follow:

(1) *Measurable objectives to be achieved from implementing corrective actions have been defined.*

Objectives represent specific conditions or changes in performance that can be quantified and measured.

(2) *Corrective actions have been reviewed before implementation to ensure that they do not cause unintended negative consequences.*

Hidden costs and risks are often associated with making changes. When large-scale changes are implemented in policies, programs, processes, procedures, or work practices, human errors become more likely during an adjustment period. In addition to the possible effects of resistance to change, some delays and difficulties in performing work may be introduced as workers are faced with unfamiliar tasks, familiar tasks to be performed in new ways, or requirements to interact with new and unfamiliar people in new jobs or in different departments.

Corrective action plans should consider potential risks and disruptions caused by implementing the changes and should provide an approach for minimizing these risks and disruptions. For example, interim processes and procedures may have to be developed to ease the transition from old work practices to new, or the corrective action plan may require that all employees affected by a change complete training before the change is implemented.

It should be noted that errors and disruptions that occur during and immediately following plan implementation may not reflect inadequacies in the corrective actions. Rather, these problems may be caused by the change process itself and inadequate planning for it.

(3) *Evaluation criteria have been defined.*

Evaluation criteria are the indicators to show that objectives (e.g., sustained elimination of adverse human performance trends) and the desired conditions to be accomplished by the corrective actions have been achieved.

(4) *Monitoring of corrective action effectiveness has been addressed.*

The desired conditions that were achieved by implementing the corrective actions may degrade as top managers change, as new programs are implemented, as the work force changes, and so on. Consequently, a plan for monitoring continued acceptable performance, including trending, is desirable.

III. COMMUNICATIONS-RELATED CRITERIA

NRC personnel conduct analyses of licensee event reports (LERs) and event investigations related to human performance at NPPs. These analyses have shown that a significant number of events involve problems with written and verbal communications among plant personnel. In fact, communications is cited as a contributing factor in as much as 35 percent of LERs involving human performance problems.

The evaluation criteria presented in Section II can also be applied to a variety of communications-related situations that occur at NPPs. For example, principles that underlie these evaluation criteria apply to verbal communications, between individuals, within and among work groups in meetings, in pre-job or pre-evolution briefings, and during shift turnovers. The evaluation

criteria can also be applied to some written communications.

Some additional specific evaluation criteria for communications problems follow:

(1) *The type of work situations have been specified in which formal communications practices are required.*

Some tasks at NPPs depend heavily on the ability of workers to coordinate their tasks and, therefore, require uniform communications practices to reduce the likelihood of communications problems. Reviews of events at NPPs suggest that uniform communications practices are necessary for the following types of communications:

- Between members of different work groups
- During shift turnover
- During remote exchanges (not face to face)
- During pre-job and pre-evolution briefings
- When planning for or performing time-critical tasks
- During periods of high workload
- When performing infrequent and unfamiliar tasks

(2) *The corrective actions define methods by which senders may verify the accuracy of the information to be communicated.*

Before composing and sending a message, senders are responsible for verifying, to the extent possible, the accuracy of the information they will be transmitting.

(3) *The corrective actions have been provided for ensuring that the level of detail in messages*

is sufficient for and tailored to the receiver's information needs.

It is essential for the sender to ensure that the information transmitted in a message provides the appropriate level of detail and highlights the important aspects of the message. In so doing, the sender tailors the message to the receiver's information needs. The sender may also need to understand the receiver's work environment and usual roles and responsibilities.

(4) *The corrective actions define vocabulary requirements.*

For written communications, such as procedures, many licensees have developed lists of acceptable common nouns and action verbs that are to be used consistently in written communications. Verbal communications may also entail the following additional requirements:

- Use simple words and phrases for concise messages.
- Avoid words that sound alike (e.g., use "lower" rather than "decrease," because "decrease" can be difficult to discriminate from "increase").
- Use the phonetic alphabet for acronyms and abbreviations ("alpha" for A, "bravo" for B, etc.).
- Use words that precisely describe what the sender expects the receiver to do or observe.

(5) *The corrective actions define methods for identifying equipment and systems.*

Identification methods should include the use of complete names, alphanumeric equipment or system identifiers, unit designator, and locations of the equipment or system.

(6) *The corrective actions define methods for identifying personnel involved in verbal communications.*

In verbal communications that do not occur face to face, senders and receivers should identify themselves at the start of the communication by giving their personal name, their job role, and their location in the plant. In circumstances in which the communicators are physically co-located but there may be more than one potential receiver (such as within-crew communications in the control room), the sender should address statements to the intended receiver and preface the statements with the receiver's name. The receiver should preface his or her verification of message receipt with the sender's name.

(7) *The corrective actions define methods for ensuring that senders and receivers understand the communications requirements of a task before the task is performed.*

These methods may include adding instructions to the procedures and work orders that will govern a task.

(8) *The corrective actions define methods for receivers to verify receipt of the message, to verify the meaning of the message, and to question conflicting or incomplete messages.*

As active participants in the communications process, receivers are responsible for notifying the sender that the message was received and for ensuring that it was accurately understood. Receivers must also maintain a questioning attitude during communications and take responsibility for clarifying with the sender any inconsistent, incomplete, or unclear messages.

(9) *The corrective actions ensure that receivers will follow up on messages that were expected but were not received.*

The timing of communications can be critical to accurate task performance. If a receiver expects information that does not arrive, it is the receiver's responsibility to seek out the information.

IV. SUMMARY

This paper has described criteria that the NRC is using to review licensee root-cause analysis, corrective actions, and implementation of corrective action plans. It also gave additional review criteria relevant to communications-related events, which exemplify a common root cause.

V. REFERENCES

"Evaluation Criteria for Communications-Related Corrective Action Plans," NUREG-1545, U.S. Nuclear Regulatory Commission, Washington, DC 20555-0001, February 1997.